

Experimental verification of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle via Single-Slit Diffraction

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1 Abstract

This experiment investigates the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (HUP) through an optical analogue using single-slit diffraction of a monochromatic He-Ne laser. The spatial confinement of light through slits of varying width is compared with the resulting diffraction patterns, providing a means to examine the relationship between position uncertainty Δx and transverse momentum uncertainty Δp_x . Diffraction patterns were recorded using a photodiode detector, and the angular positions of the first minima were determined and used to estimate the spread in momentum via the de-Broglie relation.

The results demonstrate that decreasing the width of the slit leads to an increase in the angular dispersion, corresponding to a larger uncertainty in momentum. This is consistent with the expected inverse relationship between Δx and Δp_x . The measured diffraction patterns were also found to adhere to the Fraunhofer diffraction relation, supporting the validity of the experimental model and the goodness of fit of the data.

The calculated uncertainty products were found to be of the order of 10^{-34} Js, consistent with the expected magnitude of Planck's constant. While the experimental values do not precisely satisfy the quantum mechanical bound $\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \hbar/2$, they are consistent with the order-of-magnitude prediction obtained from diffraction theory.

These findings support the interpretation of diffraction as a classical manifestation of the Fourier relationship between position and momentum space, providing a physically intuitive demonstration of the uncertainty principle. Limitations due to measurement resolution, detector sensitivity, and the restricted number of slit widths are acknowledged.

2 Introduction and Aim

The Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle is a fundamental result in Quantum Mechanics, asserting that any physical object can be probabilistically described through a wave function. There exists some pair of physical properties, position \mathbf{x} and momentum \mathbf{p} which are simultaneously unknowable with arbitrary precision. In this experiment, we attempt to compare the results of optical diffraction through a single slit with monochromatic He-Ne light source. Thus, permitting us to compare the results of optical light to support the non-deterministic characteristics of Quantum Mechanics through the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (HUP).

The objective of this experiment is to experimentally demonstrate the relationship between spatial confinement and momentum uncertainty through diffraction patterns produced by light passing through single slits of varying width.

3 Theory

3.1 Formalized Derivation

The Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle arises from the properties of the uncertainty of non-commuting operators in Quantum Mechanics. For an observable A , the standard deviation or uncertainty is defined as

$$(\Delta A)^2 = \langle (A - \langle A \rangle)^2 \rangle.$$

This is similar for an observable B ,

$$(\Delta B)^2 = \langle (B - \langle B \rangle)^2 \rangle.$$

Applying the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality to the initial state ψ :
We obtain

- $(A - \langle A \rangle)\psi$
- $(B - \langle B \rangle)\psi$

using the Cauchy–Schwarz and utilising the commutator relation
 $[A, B] = AB - BA$
we obtain the general uncertainty relation

$$\Delta A \Delta B \geq \frac{1}{2} |\langle [A, B] \rangle|,$$

where for x and p_x , the commutation relation is

$$[x, p_x] = i\hbar.$$

Substituting into the general uncertainty relation

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}.$$

This establishes a fundamental lower bound on the simultaneous precision with which position and momentum can be known. Or, as an order of magnitude approximation which differs from the exact bound by a factor of 2π

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \approx h$$

3.2 Optical Derivation

We then consider a the optical derivation which provides a heuristic illustration of the HUP. Optical waves passes through a single slit, undergoes diffraction and scatters across a detector screen. Similarly, a particle can also be described by a wave function, with uncertainty in position Δx and momentum Δp . This uncertainty in position and momentum arises from the Fourier transform between position-space and momentum-space distribution, where the narrowing of one increases the spread of the other.

If we consider now the perspective of the laser source using wave particle duality(1905), We note that the light passing through the single slit can also be considered as a stream of wavelets (photons), consistent with wave particle duality.

Consider a particle passing through a slit of width a . Its uncertainty in position in the x -direction is approximately

$$\Delta x \approx a$$

As the particle passes through the slit, it undergoes diffraction. The first minimum of the diffraction pattern occurs at an angle θ given by

$$a \sin \theta = m\lambda$$

and where $m = 1$, and λ is the wavelength of the light source. Using small angle approximation, where $\sin \theta \approx \theta$ is valid for $\theta \lesssim 15^\circ$.

$$\sin \theta \approx \theta \approx \frac{\lambda}{a}$$

Figure 1: Typical diffraction of light source after passing through a single slit with width a .

Figure 2: Momentum-space probability distribution after passing through a single slit

We can then represent the uncertainty in momentum using the first order minima, with this diffraction implying an uncertainty in the particle's momentum in the direction of the screen Δp . Using the de Broglie relation, the uncertainty in the x -component of momentum is approximately

$$\Delta p_x \approx p \sin \theta$$

Substituting the above expression gives the following expression.

$$\Delta p_x \approx \frac{h}{\lambda} \cdot \sin \theta$$

this gives

$$\Delta p_x \approx \frac{h}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{\lambda}{a}$$

which simplifies to

$$\Delta p_x \approx \frac{h}{a}$$

Substituting $a \approx \Delta x$ gives

$$\Delta p_x \approx \frac{h}{\Delta x}$$

and therefore the lower approximation of

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \approx h$$

This heuristic derivation provides some physical intuition for the uncertainty relation. A rigorous Quantum Mechanics derivation using Operators shows that the exact lower bound is

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}.$$

We measure the angular position of the first diffraction minima and using small angle approximation, we provide estimation of the momentum uncertainty Δp_x . By comparing this with the slit width a , we evaluate the relationship between Δx and Δp_x .

3.3 Physical interpretation

To determine an electron's position, it must be probed by a photon. A shorter wavelength photon will provide higher spatial resolution, however, its large momentum induces a larger unpredictable momentum in the electron. Similarly, a longer wavelength photon will provide worse spatial accuracy but also reduces the unpredictability in the momentum. This effect is observed during scattering in the Compton Effect [1923]. And reflects a an intuitive interpretation of the effects of HUP due to the intrinsic uncertain nature of particles rather than measurement limitations.

3.4 Diffraction from a Single Slit

We can visualize the diffraction patterns from Fraunhofer using the Huygens principle of a uniform wavefront made up of wavelets. We can split the wave front up in N beams.

Thus, we divide the slit width a into N equal lengths of δa .

from the geometry above, we note that the path difference (p.d.) of each wavelet are equal, the angles between successive wavelets are also equal. This is because the slices of the slit a all have equal width and length, so the phase difference are equal too.

The full phase difference across the slit is given by

$$\frac{2\pi a \sin(\theta)}{\lambda}$$

If we then picture an phasor addition involving all N of these wavelets, we can then sum these wavelets up into a circular outline. And as N approaches infinity, the resultant shape becomes more and more like an arc.

We'll call the angle that this subtends 2α . Now 2α is also the phase difference between the first and the last phasor across the full slit, which is also double the exact angle between the first minima and the central maxima.

Figure 3: Wave front divided into N beams after passing through a single slit

Figure 4: Vector addition of N phases in a circle, with maximum magnitude and phase difference

$$\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} a \sin(\theta)$$

therefore

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi a \sin \theta}{\lambda}.$$

The phasor sum has magnitude A , which we can write as $R \sin \alpha$, with R as the radius of the arc. On the center spot of the pattern, where the phasors are all in phase, the phasor sum is the straight line shown in red at right. This is also the amplitude of the diffraction pattern at $\theta \neq 0$, which we call A_0 . By the definition of angle, $2\alpha = A_0/R$, which gives us $R = A_0/2\alpha$. So the magnitude of the phasor sum is

$$A = 2R \sin \alpha = \frac{A_0 \sin \alpha}{\alpha}.$$

Since the intensity I is always proportional to square of the amplitude. So, using I_0 for the intensity at the centre of the pattern, we have

$$I = I_0 \left(\frac{\sin \alpha}{\alpha} \right)^2 \quad \text{where} \quad \alpha = \frac{\pi a \sin \theta}{\lambda}.$$

Also known as the sinc² function. In which the first diffraction minimum will occur at $\alpha = \pi$, giving the condition $a \sin \theta = \lambda$ which is used to determine the angular momentum spread experimentally.

4 Experimental Setup

The aim of this experiment was to observe and measure the intensity of the diffraction pattern, the overview of the entire experiment setup is shown below in the figure.

The primary components include a helium neon (He/Ne) laser, a diaphragm containing 3 single slits of different widths, a detection slit mounted in front of a photocell, as well as a photo amplifier and digital multimeter.

The laser produces monochromatic light with wavelength of

$$\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$$

This produced the output power of approximately 1mW, which is classified as a class 2 laser. So the following safety precautions are taken during setup

Precaution 1: Avoid staring into the laser source for longer than the blink reflex duration (0.25 s)

Precaution 2: Take off all reflective jewelry and watches

Precaution 3: Ensuring to not point the laser at other people

The laser beam was directed toward a diaphragm containing three single slits with widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm.

The selected slit diffracted the laser beam and produced a single-slit diffraction pattern along the optical bench.

Behind the optical bench, the diffraction pattern was detected using a photocell positioned behind a measurement slit of width approximately 0.3 mm. This measurement slit was mounted via a translation stage controlled by a multiple turn dial counters, which allows precise lateral movement across the diffraction pattern.

The signal from the photocell was then amplified using a photo amplifier and the resulting voltage output was measured using a multimeter. The voltage reading will be proportional to the intensity of the incident light at any point along the photocell, thus, enabling the measurement of spatial intensity distributed across the diffraction pattern.

All of these components were mounted on a 1.5 m optical bench to ensure precise alignment of the entire optical system.

5 Methodology

Prior to data collection, the He/Ne laser was warmed up for approximately 30 minutes to ensure that the output intensity reached operational level. During this period each optical component was inspected and properly aligned.

- Step 1: One of the single slits was picked and positioned in the laser beam by laterally moving the slide holder containing the apertures.
- Step 2: Both the slit and the photocell detector was aligned carefully to allow for the central maximum to propagate straight through, care was taken to adjust the angle of the laser to ensure maximal reading during calibration.
- Step 3: The photocell was then moved so that the beam was pointing outside the left first-order maximum.
- Step 4: The measurement slit in front of the photocell was translated laterally across the diffraction pattern using the multiple-turn dial counter.
- Step 5: At each 0.40 mm, or 1/3 of a revolution, measurements were taken through the digital multimeter. Care was taken to ensure precision through eye-level reading and a brief 5 second pause was allowed to minimise multimeter noise.
- Step 6: For each slit width (0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm), a full intensity profile was obtained by repeating step 1 - step 5. Recording a sequence of voltage measurements from the left first-order maximum to the right first-order maximum.

The slit-to-detector distance, laser wavelength, slit width, and translation resolution were all important parameters, and kept uniform across all 3 slits.

This counter provided a stable relationship between the angle of the beam split and the corresponding voltage difference taken at the multimeter.

The voltage output was recorded at equidistant points along this sweep and allowed inference of a relationship between angular spread and intensity of the diffraction pattern at that position.

The resulting data provided the spatial intensity distribution of the diffraction pattern for each slit width. These intensity profiles were subsequently analyzed to determine the spread of the diffracted beam and to investigate the relationship between slit width Δx and momentum uncertainty Δp .

To minimize systematic errors associated with the mechanical backlash in the dial counter, measurements were taken by sweeping the slit continuously in one direction across the diffraction pattern, though some data points may still have errors from backlash due to unfamiliarity with the turn dial counter.

6 Data and Results

6.1 Raw and Normalized Diffraction Profiles

The experimental datasets were imported from the measurement spreadsheet using the MATLAB `readtable` function. Three complete slits corresponding to the widths of the slits of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm were then extracted for analysis.

Basic data validation was performed by removing rows containing missing values or NaN entries. After cleaning, three valid displacement-voltage datasets were obtained for subsequent processing.

To enable direct comparison between datasets, the measured signals were normalized. The background signal was estimated by averaging the first and last five voltage measurements of each dataset. These correspond to approximately 5/139, 5/99, and 5/45 of the total data points for the respective slits.

These points were assumed to lie outside the central diffraction maximum where the optical intensity approaches zero. The resulting average value therefore represents the ambient electronic offset of the photocell and multimeter.

Figure 5: Raw diffraction patterns measured for slit widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits.

This background value was subtracted from the entire dataset. Any negative values resulting from the subtraction were set to zero. The corrected signal was then normalized by dividing by the maximum measured voltage in each dataset.

The photocell voltage is proportional to the optical intensity of the diffraction pattern. After normalization, the measured voltage therefore represents the relative diffraction intensity. This transformation allows the diffraction profiles for different slit widths to be directly compared.

6.2 First Minima and Central Diffraction Width

Each diffraction data set was divided into the left and right regions relative to the central maximum. The minimum intensity point on each side was identified and taken to represent the first diffraction minimum.

During the experimental measurements, data were intentionally collected only within the region containing the first diffraction maximum. This ensured that the recorded diffraction pattern included the central peak and its first minima on both sides. The validity of this assumption is confirmed by the shape of the raw diffraction profiles shown. 5.

The distance between the left and right minima was then taken as the experimental width of the central diffraction maximum,

$$\Delta x = x_R - x_L$$

which corresponds to the spread of all the diffraction patterns (see table below).

Trial	Nominal Slit Width (mm)	Left Min (mm)	Right Min (mm)
Trial 1	0.1	-9.1000	8.9000
Trial 2	0.2	-5.2000	6.2000
Trial 3	0.4	-1.8000	6.7000

Table 1: Measured diffraction minima for varying slit widths.

Only the data points located between these two minima were retained for model fitting so that the analysis focused exclusively on the central diffraction maximum.

The resulting normalised diffraction profiles for the three slit widths are shown in. 6.

Figure 6: Normalised diffraction profiles of the central maxima for slit widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits .

6.3 Model fits

To quantify the shape of the central diffraction peak, both a Gaussian model and a sinc² model were fitted with normalized datasets of each slit. The Gaussian fit provided a convenient empirical estimate of FWHM and data point spread, whereas the sinc² fit represented the theoretical Fraunhofer diffraction form above. Residual plots and RMSE values were used to compare the fit quality.

6.3.1 Gaussian Fit

A Gaussian function was fitted to the central diffraction peak,

$$I(x) = a_1 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x - b_1}{c_1} \right)^2 \right],$$

Figure 7: Gaussian fit profiles of the central maxima for slit widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits.

where a_1 represents the peak intensity, b_1 is the center position of the peak, and c_1 characterizes the spread of the distribution.

Although the diffraction pattern is not strictly Gaussian, this model provides a convenient empirical approximation of the central peak. In particular, the Gaussian width parameter allows estimation of the full width at half maximum (FWHM), given by

$$\text{FWHM} = 2\sqrt{\ln 2} c_1.$$

The fitted parameters and their confidence intervals were obtained using least squares fitting. The resulting FWHM values provide an experimental measure of the width of the central diffraction maximum (See table below).

Trial	Peak Intensity (units)	FWHM (mm)
Trial 1	1.0039 ± 0.0353	9.8711 ± 0.3844
Trial 2	1.0296 ± 0.0523	4.8213 ± 0.2825
Trial 3	2.9799 ± 0.5218	2.7526 ± 0.1598

Table 2: Peak intensity and FWHM measurements of the Gaussian fit per trial.

6.3.2 sinc^2 Fit

The theoretical intensity distribution for Fraunhofer diffraction from a single slit is

$$I(\theta) = I_0 \left(\frac{\sin \beta}{\beta} \right)^2,$$

where

Figure 8: Sinc-squared fit profiles of the central maxima for slit widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits.

$$\beta = \frac{\pi a \sin \theta}{\lambda},$$

a is the slit width and λ is the wavelength of the light.

For small diffraction angles, the detector position x is related to the angle by

$$\theta \approx \frac{x}{L},$$

where L is the distance between the slit and the detector. Substituting this relation gives an intensity profile proportional to

$$I(x) = A \operatorname{sinc}^2[B(x - x_0)],$$

where A is the peak intensity, x_0 is the central peak position, and B is a parameter related to the slit width.

This physically motivated sinc^2 model was fitted to the experimental data using nonlinear least squares. From the fitted parameter B , an estimate of the slit width could be obtained through the relation

$$a = \frac{B\lambda L}{\pi}.$$

The fitted slit widths were then compared with the nominal slit values provided in the experimental setup. See table below for goodness of fit plots between slits.

Trial	Gaussian Model		sinc ² Model	
	RMSE	χ^2	RMSE	χ^2
Trial 1	0.0535	44.8458	0.0444	30.9237
Trial 2	0.0521	24.1871	0.0513	23.4890
Trial 3	0.0481	26.0623	0.2447	674.5851

Table 3: Statistical comparison of Gaussian vs. sinc² fitting models.

6.3.3 Comparison of Fits

To determine which model better described the experimental diffraction pattern, the Gaussian and sinc² fits were compared using their residual distributions and root mean square error (RMSE).

Figure 9: Residual plots of both fits for comparison for slit widths of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits.

Residual plots were inspected to determine whether systematic deviations were present. The sinc² model provides a good approximation for the 0.1 mm and 0.2 mm smaller slits, where the diffraction pattern was captured with more data and more completely.

However, for the widest slit (0.4 mm), the diffraction pattern was significantly narrower than for the other slits. As a result, the multimeter was unable to capture a significant portion of the readings beyond a certain upper voltage threshold. This resulted in the measured data being inconsistent and having a rise and fall profile with a flat line middle. As a result, the sinc² model fit performed poorly and the inferred slit width from the fit deviated from the nominal value.

Overall, in a well captured data with correct equipment, we can denote the sinc² fit to be more suitable as it provided an RSME of 0.0444 compared to the Gaussian's 0.0535 in trial 1, and the RSME of 0.0513 compared to the Gaussian's 0.0521 in trial 2. Denoting an better fit in trial 1 and trial 2. however, we also note that its RSME value is particularly high in trial 3, at 0.2447 compared to the Gaussian's 0.0481. This trend indicates that whilst an unsaturated, low error distribution does indeed support a good sinc² relation, the Gaussian does give a smoother approximation when between overall slits conducted. This is further

supported by the χ^2 value provided of 44.85, 24.18 and 26.06 for the Gaussian relation, and 30.92, 23.48 and 674.5 for the sinc² relation. This comparison of the fits validates the relation between uncertain in position Δx and momentum Δp_x can indeed be approximated heuristically through a sinc² fit when considering intensity and diffraction of photons passing through a single slit.

6.3.4 Random Noise

The difference between slits could arise from measurement uncertainty of many sources. Including the resolution of the displacement dial and the voltage measurement from the multimeter, and many other sources of uncertainty from instrument and the environment. To estimate the resulting uncertainty in the measured diffraction width between slits. a Monte Carlo simulation was performed to instil an approximated random noise which is the mean of the total margin of uncertainties.

Figure 10: MC random noise plots to simulate mean measurement uncertainty of 0.1 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.4 mm slits.

In this approach, random noise consistent with the mean measurement resolution was added to the normalised intensity data. The noise amplitude was estimated from the measurement resolution using the lower bound of the RMS of all the **significant** uncertainties (given below) with the value of 0.2. Thus,

$$\sigma_I = \frac{\text{resolution}}{\sqrt{12}}$$

which correctly corresponds to the standard deviation of a uniform measurement uncertainty.

For each slit, 10 000 simulated diffractions profiles were generated through adding random noise to the measured resultant (intensity value). For every simulated dataset, the positions of the first minima and central maximum were recalculated with

$$w = x_R - x_L$$

The distribution of simulated widths provides an estimate of the statistical uncertainty in the maxima profile. The mean value of the simulated distribution gives the best estimate of the width (marked in color),

while the standard deviation of the distribution provides the uncertainty.

Histograms of the simulated width distributions for each slit are shown in 10. The resulting uncertainties were used as error bars in subsequent analysis, including the verification of the diffraction width dependence on inverse slit width.

6.4 Verification of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Relation

The experiment also allows qualitative verification of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle by relating the slit width to the spread of the diffraction pattern.

The slit width a constrains the transverse position of photons passing through the aperture. This confinement produces an uncertainty in the transverse momentum of the photons, which manifests as angular spreading of the diffraction pattern.

The angular spread of the first diffraction minimum is approximately

$$\sin \theta \approx \frac{\lambda}{a}.$$

Using the small-angle approximation, the transverse momentum uncertainty can be estimated as

$$\Delta p_x \approx \frac{h}{\lambda} \sin \theta.$$

The position uncertainty is taken as the slit width,

$$\Delta x \approx a.$$

For each slit width, the uncertainty product

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x$$

The sum was calculated. As the slit width decreases, the diffraction pattern broadens and the momentum uncertainty increases. The calculated uncertainty products were found to be in the order of 10^{-34} Js, consistent with the expected scale set by Planck's constant.

Although the experiment is limited by measurement resolution and systematic uncertainties, the results demonstrate the qualitative behavior predicted by the Heisenberg uncertainty principle: greater confinement in position leads to increased uncertainty in momentum. This is represented fully in the results table below

Position Uncertainty (Δx)	Momentum (Δp)	Uncertainty	Uncertainty Product
0.0001	9.4114×10^{-30}		9.4114×10^{-34}
0.0002	5.9606×10^{-30}		1.1921×10^{-33}
0.0004	4.4443×10^{-30}		1.7777×10^{-33}

Table 4: Heisenberg uncertainty principle verification data.

7 Uncertainty

7.1 Uncertainty types

Uncertainties from this experiment can be classified according to both statistical (Type A) and instrumental/systematic (Type B) sources. This way, we are able to accordingly determine the source, scaling and propagation of each uncertainty source and their impact on precision. We also determine if each uncertainty source is **significant** or **not significant** and can be neglected.

7.1.1 instrumental uncertainties (Type B)

Slit width tolerance Manufacturer tolerances of the slits introduces uncertainty in the position of the initial photon slits.

$$a = 0.1, 0.2, 0.4 \text{ mm}$$

each with a tolerance of approximately 10%:

This directly determines the position uncertainty of

$$\frac{\delta a}{a} = 0.10$$

$$\delta a = \begin{cases} 0.01 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.1 \text{ mm}) \\ 0.02 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.2 \text{ mm}) \\ 0.04 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.4 \text{ mm}) \end{cases}$$

Thus, we observe a large uncertainty in each slits used, therefore the uncertainty propagation from this variable **is significant**.

dial counter calibration The multi-turn dial counter translates the detector laterally across the diffraction pattern. Calibration of measurement increments yields

$$1 \text{ dial unit} = 2 \text{ mm}$$

The estimated parallax uncertainty is

$$\delta x \approx \pm 0.5 \text{ mm.}$$

For a typical first minima position of approximately

$$x \approx 10 \text{ mm}$$

the relative uncertainty becomes

$$\frac{\delta x}{x} = \frac{0.5}{10} = 0.05 = 5\%$$

Thus, we observe a large uncertainty in each minima position used, therefore the uncertainty propagation from this variable **is significant**.

Mechanical backlash Mechanical backlash in the screw gear mechanism may also introduce an additional partial systematic uncertainty once the translation direction is reversed (see 0.1 mm slit trial).

with a tolerance of approximately 10% determined qualitatively from the fit:

$$\frac{\delta a}{a} = 0.10$$

$$\delta a = \begin{cases} 0.01 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.1 \text{ mm}) \\ 0.02 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.2 \text{ mm}) \\ 0.04 \text{ mm} & (a = 0.4 \text{ mm}) \end{cases}$$

However, even as the relative uncertainty contribution is significant, since the magnitude of the effect is not systematic, independently calibrated and only occurred sporadically in the earlier slits. This effect will be treated qualitatively and not be included in the numerical uncertainty propagation and is **not significant**.

Slit–detector distance This distance was measured using a meter bench ruler. This uncertainty propagated into the angular estimate later on.

$$L = 1.001 \pm 0.0005 \text{ m}$$

$$\theta \approx \frac{x}{L}.$$

However, as the markings of the meter ruler are quite precise. this relative uncertainty source is only 0.05% and therefore **not significant**.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta L}{L} &= \frac{0.0005}{1.001} \approx 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \\ &\approx 0.05\%. \end{aligned}$$

Laser wavelength The correct He–Ne laser wavelength is

$$\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$$

with a manufacturer tolerance of approximately

$$\frac{\delta \lambda}{\lambda} = 0.1\%.$$

This contribution is negligible compared to geometric uncertainties and is **not significant**.

Detector aperture width The photodiode detector uses a measurement slit of width

$$w_d = 0.3 \text{ mm}.$$

For a diffraction peak width of approximately

$$W \approx 20 \text{ mm},$$

Thus, as the 0.3 mm slit is mounted in front of the photodiode and can limit the spatial resolution and averages the intensity profile the diffraction pattern. This effect directly contributes the resultant wave profile. Thus, limiting the spatial intensity profile and is **significant**.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{w_d}{W} &= \frac{0.3}{20} = 0.015 \\ &= 1.5\%. \end{aligned}$$

Voltage measurement resolution The digital multimeter resolution is approximately

$$\delta V \approx \pm 0.01 \text{ V}.$$

For a typical signal level of

$$V \approx 1.0 \text{ V},$$

the relative uncertainty becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta V}{V} &= \frac{0.01}{1.0} = 0.01 \\ &= 1\%. \end{aligned}$$

This is **significant**.

7.1.2 Statistical uncertainties (Type A)

Electronic noise Noise in the power supply/photocell–amplifier circuit can introduce random fluctuations or signal drift in the recorded voltage signal. This is **not significant**.

Background offset Ambient light and detector dark current produce a baseline voltage offset. However, this was removed by subtracting the average voltage measured at the edges of each dataset. This is **not significant**.

Minima localization The first diffraction minima are determined from discretely sampled detector positions, introducing uncertainty due to the sampling interval.

The diffraction minima were determined from discretely sampled detector positions with a step size of

$$\Delta x = 0.4 \text{ mm.}$$

The uncertainty in locating the minima can therefore be approximated as

$$\delta x_{min} \approx \frac{\Delta x}{2}$$

$$\delta x_{min} \approx 0.2 \text{ mm.}$$

For the mean minima position of $x \approx 10$ mm this is **significant**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta x_{min}}{x} &= \frac{0.2}{10} = 0.02 \\ &= 2\%. \end{aligned}$$

Monte Carlo propagation To quantify the combined effects of the measurement noise from instruments, a Monte Carlo Simulation with 10^4 slits was performed. Random noise consistent with the resolutions was added to the intensity data. After which the maxima width was recalculated each time. This resulting distribution width provided a more comprehensible understanding of statistical uncertainty.

7.2 Total uncertainty

Assuming the uncertainties are independent, the combined systematic and statistical uncertainty can be estimated using the familiar quadratic error propagation. The **significant** relative uncertainties arise from the following sources:

(slit width tolerance = 0.10; dial counter resolution = 0.02; detector aperture average = 0.015; voltage measurement resolution = 0.01; minima localization = 0.02).

The total relative uncertainty is therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta Q}{Q} &= \sqrt{(0.10)^2 + (0.02)^2 + (0.015)^2 + (0.01)^2 + (0.02)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{0.011125} \approx 0.105. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the total experimental uncertainty is approximately

$$\frac{\delta Q}{Q} \approx 10.5\%.$$

The overall uncertainty is dominated by the slit width tolerance (10%), while the remainder contributions: dial counter resolution (2%), detector aperture averaging (1.5%), voltage resolution (1%), and minima localisation (2%) are comparatively smaller contributions.

8 Discussion

The experimental result demonstrated the expected inverse relationship between slit width and diffraction spread. After the full measured maxima width at FWHM decreased from

9.8711 ± 0.3844 mm for the 0.1 mm slit, to 4.8213 ± 0.2825 mm for the 0.2 mm slit, and to 2.7526 ± 0.1598 mm for the 0.4 mm slit.

We are able to demonstrate with a factor of 2, that this is in fact consistent with the single slit diffraction theory. A narrower slit produces a broader diffraction pattern due to more spread in the wave.

This result was then used to calculate and verify the HUP

$$\Delta x \Delta p_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

through the correspondence between slit width (a) and Δx , angular maxima spread ($1/w$) and Δp_x . This showed that while the angular spread in the first order maxima increased, this corresponded to a greater uncertainty in the transverse momentum. The final calculated uncertainty products were all of the order 10^{-34} J s and 10^{-33} J s. This result is consistent in order of magnitude with the expected value for Planck's constant of 6.626×10^{-34} J s. The experiment did not provide a precise verification of the formalised lower bound. Instead it provided a reasonably accurate result given both statistical and instrumental uncertainty.

Comparison of the Gaussian and the sinc^2 fit shows that the sinc^2 was a better fit in the narrower slits of 0.1 mm and 0.2 mm. In the 0.1 mm slit, the sinc^2 fit gave both a lower RMSE and lower χ^2 value than the Gaussian fit, while for 0.2 mm slit both models performed similarly with the sinc^2 fit slightly better. This is as expected as the Fraunhofer diffraction pattern from a single slit is theoretically described by a sinc^2 intensity distribution, whereas the Gaussian fit is more empirical approximation of many typical fits.

The cause of the deviations of the 0.4 mm slit can be explained by the widest slit producing the narrowest diffraction pattern with the biggest intensity. Due to the saturation effect of our multimeter above a threshold voltage of 2.76 V. we were hence unable to capture any meaningful data beyond the two minima troughs. As a result, errors in detector aperture, limited resolution and voltage saturation all had significant influence on the recorded profile. Although there is still sufficient data to verify the trend of decreased spread of Δp due to higher Δx . calculated goodness of fit, slit width and the 0.4 mm slit should be analyzed with caution.

Overall, the experiment successfully reproduced the expected diffraction behavior and demonstrated the qualitative connection between position confinement and momentum uncertainty. The results support the theoretical prediction that narrower slits produce larger diffraction spreads, and the uncertainty products were found to be of the correct order of magnitude. While the experiment was limited by instrumental resolution and slit tolerance, it nevertheless provided a meaningful experimental illustration of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle.

8.1 Validity

The experiment setup sufficiently valid. Some measures were taken to approximate the external noise and interference sources. The use of rigorous uncertainty and fits provides strong evidence for a valid experimental analysis. Therefore, whilst the experiment itself is valid for the purpose of verification. Cleaner lab pipeline are desirable for comparison of exact values.

8.2 Accuracy

The experiment was mostly accurate, as measurement scale, calibration and aperture and laser sources were all considered. Therefore, making the experiment a good example of verification of approximations of both the Fraunhofer intensity profile and the HUP.

8.3 Precision

Although the experiment was conducted in a professional student lab environment, using equipment provided such as

PHYWE slits

LASOS 633 nm laser

optical benches

optical bench ruler

professional optics mounts, gears and dials

It nonetheless was only able to give a marginally precise result as the margin of error for exact measurements were small and the imprecision of a single error source propagated throughout the calculations. Hence, more precise optics equipment is definitely desirable to achieve more exact comparable figures.

8.4 Reliability

The experiment is unable to be verified through multiple iterations for each slit, however, the setup between slits were identical except for the position of the turn dial counter.

Thus, whilst the methods deployed may have been reliable, there was insufficient equipment provided to ensure the reproducibility of results over similar equipment, and equipment which are of the higher precision should be utilized to ensure reliability. Additionally, iterative slits of each slit should definitely be considered to improve reliability.

9 limitations

Only a limited number of slit widths were used, restricting the ability to rigorously verify proportionality between Δx and Δp_x .

limited reliability

limited precision

10 Conclusion

This experiment successfully verified trends from both the Fraunhofer intensity profile of a central maxima, as well as the trends in the HUP. Key properties such as aperture widths, voltage and measurement length were extracted with reasonable accuracy and precision. However, highly accurate data was unable to be verified due to a lack of iterative testing and saturation of the voltage. Overall, the experiment provided good understanding of the verification of the physics of optical diffraction through a single slit with monochromatic He-Ne light source, which illustrates a heuristic view of a fundamental corollary of the non deterministic nature of Quantum Mechanics.

A Appendix A: Bibliography and Resources

MATLAB and Code Resources

The data processing, curve fitting, and analysis were performed using MATLAB. The following documentation was used:

- MathWorks, *MATLAB Documentation*. Available at: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/matlab/>
- Curve fitting functions: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/curvefit/fit.html>
- Confidence intervals: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/curvefit/cfit.confint.html>
- Sinc function: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/signal/ref/sinc.html>
- Linear fitting: <https://www.mathworks.com/help/stats/fitlm.html>
- Numerical integration (trapz): <https://www.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/trapz.html>

Theoretical References

Textbook references

- D. J. Griffiths, *Introduction to Electrodynamics*, 4th ed., Pearson, 2013.
- D. J. Griffiths and D. F. Schroeter, *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics*, 3rd ed., Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- E. Hecht, *Optics*, 5th ed., Pearson, 2017.

Supplementary references:

- <https://crackingthenutshell.org/heisenbergs-uncertainty-principle/>
- <https://pressbooks.online.ucf.edu/phy2054lt/chapter/single-slit-diffraction/>
- https://lipa.physics.oregonstate.edu/sec_single-slit-diffraction.html

The format and template itself is a variation of Overleaf. (n.d.). *NTNU laboratory report in physics*. Overleaf. <https://www.overleaf.com/latex/templates/ntnu-laboratory-report-in-physics/zrksxtqtpdpv>

And lastly, all AI syntax assistance usage are from:

OpenAI, 2026. *ChatGPT (GPT-5.3)* [Large language model]. <https://chat.openai.com/>
Google, 2026. *Gemini* [Large language model]. <https://gemini.google.com/>

A Appendix B: Lab Notes

Prelab

1 Fraunhofer condition met when $D \gg \frac{a^2}{\lambda}$

$a = 0.1 - 0.4 \text{ mm.}$

calculate for largest aperture: $\frac{(0.4 \times 10^{-3})^2}{632.8 \times 10^{-9}} = 0.25 < 1$ & yes

2. $m=1 (0.1 \times 10^{-3}) \sin(\alpha) = 632.8 \text{ nm}$ $\alpha = 0.363^\circ$

$m=2. (0.1 \times 10^{-3}) \sin(\alpha) = 2 \times 632.8 \text{ nm}$ $\alpha = 0.725^\circ$

$m=3 (0.1 \times 10^{-3}) \sin(\alpha) = 3 \times 632.8 \text{ nm}$ $\alpha = 1.088^\circ$

3. as $\Delta x \Delta p \leq \frac{h}{2}$, we change the slit width will adjust Δx .

as slit width is narrow. $\Delta x \downarrow$, $\Delta p \uparrow$ and diffraction angle spreads

as slit width becomes wide $\Delta x \uparrow$, $\Delta p \downarrow$ and diffraction pattern narrows.

4. a. $\lambda = \frac{h}{p} = \frac{h}{mv}$ $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = 1.011$ $p = \gamma mv = 4.141 \times 10^{-23}$

$\lambda = \frac{h}{p} = 1.599 \times 10^{-11}$ $d = \frac{\lambda}{\sin(\alpha)} = 2.52 \text{ nm}$

b. $m = \frac{M}{N_A} = \frac{60 \times 0.012}{6.022 \times 10^{23}} \approx 1.196 \times 10^{-24} \text{ kg}$ $\lambda = \frac{h}{p} = 2.518 \times 10^{-12}$

$p = mv = 2.6312 \times 10^{-22} \text{ kg/m/s.}$ $m=1$ $d = \frac{\lambda}{\sin(\alpha)} = 0.397 \text{ nm}$

Lab

formula on notes: pg 316 of procedure

- error: $\sqrt{(\Delta p)}$

- use $\lambda = \frac{h}{p}$ $\lambda \uparrow$ $p \downarrow$

- find Δx . Δp .

- find minima.

- result on excel.

- L and a are known

A Appendix C: Matlab code

<https://github.com/Skippertheev/Experiment-data-analysis/tree/cd3aef154208130194cf7892dbe00de4265a1617/HUP%20experiment>